

CIPP, non-destructive technologies for pipe rehabilitation in real estate assets

Operational instructions

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1. Abstract

The purpose of this dissertation is to identify the best method for rehabilitating small-diameter pipes. In the field of water supply systems and functional pipe rehabilitation, small-diameter refers to pipes with a diameter smaller than DN 300. A DN 300 pipe typically represents the diameter of a discharge pipe in a large multi-story building connected to the blackwater or combined drainage system. For instance, a seven-story building with a floor area ranging between 1500 and 2000 m² per floor may have a main collector of this size in the basement levels.

The topic of pipe rehabilitation is significant in the maintenance of large real estate assets that are no longer new, particularly in buildings over 60-70 years old located in the centre of large cities like Milan. This issue cannot be overlooked, as a sudden failure reduces the usability of the property, forcing the building manager to perform emergency maintenance and face the associated challenges.

Maintenance contracts for repairing failures, regardless of the intervention method, include binding conditions for contractors. These constraints, typically imposed by the clients, often focus on rapid execution, minimizing interactions with public authorities, and ensuring low environmental impact (noise, dust, and occupation of public \ private room). Within this context, the functional rehabilitation of old pipes, using the internal relining method based on polymerized resin, has gained considerable traction. This method involves the use of specialized equipment, materials, composite materials, and specific know-how.

The fundamental principle of the method is outlined below: the adhesion of a liner to the host pipe through the inversion of a flexible tube. The inversion and inflation of the tube occur simultaneously, and in more advanced machinery, the same machine also performs the resin polymerization using ultraviolet (UV) radiation. The components of the method will be presented, along with the procedure for restoring the functionality of the entire discharge pipe.

This procedure was invented by the British engineer Eric Wood in 1971, who developed a method to meet all the constraints set by building owners. The method is widely adopted because it allows for easy transportation and handling of both materials and equipment on-site.

This technique is known by the acronym **CIPP** (Cured-In-Place Pipe), and its significance is highlighted by the name that the inventor gave to his company, **INSITUFORM**, which in Latin means "formed in place." At the end of the dissertation, a series of photos is included to provide a clearer understanding of the process.

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2. **Keywords:** Rainwater Leakage, No-Dig Technology, Pipe Maintenance, CIPP, Cure In Place Pipe, downpipe, Relining, Pipe Rehabilitation, Liner, Liner Inversion, Eversion

3. Definitions and acronyms

MTBF	Mean Time Between failures
CIPP:	Technology to provide a cured in place pipe
DN:	Nominal diameter
Curing:	Process of resin polymerisation by the use of heat or exposure to light.
Composite:	Composition of elements in sheets or membranes assembled to provide the required requirements.
Lining tube:	A flexible tube, consisting of a liner which carries the liquid resin during insertion into the pipe, membranes to create a structural thickness.
Replacement:	Rehabilitation of an existing piping system by installing a new piping system, without incorporating original artifacts
Eversion:	Process of turning a flexible tube inside out using water or air pressure.
Pot life:	A chemical reaction index that indicates the time within which the resin can be applied before the polymerisation process and the resulting increase in viscosity begin, making the resin no longer workable
Everted-in-place insertion:	The method by which an impregnated lining tube is introduced by eversion to achieve simultaneous insertion both insertion and inflation.
Winched -in-place insertion:	The method whereby a flat impregnated liner is pulled into the pipe and then inflated so that it can adhere to the pipe.
Inflation can be achieved by means	an air compressor and a hose inside the liner which can be withdrawn after resin cure.
Rehabilitation:	All measures to restore or improve the performance of an existing pipeline
Internal membrane:	Membrane which forms the inside surface of the pipe after installation.

4. Introduction

In the management of prestigious real estate assets, typically located in city centres, the buildings are often over 60 years old. According to construction best practices, a non-pressurized discharge pipe

should be replaced once it reaches its useful life limit of 50 years. It is well known that operating a machine or system beyond its useful life threshold necessitates continuous maintenance, as the failure rate tends to increase rapidly, as shown in the following classical bath-tube curve figure.

Below is a table of scheduled maintenance interventions for the pipes in question, where it is evident that the common practice of replacing pipes at 50 years is authoritatively confirmed by French standard norms (NF).

Blackwater and wastewater discharge pipe			
Operations	Frequency	Value %	Standard norms
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inspections Visual inspection of inspectable collectors 	yearly	1%	NF P 16-100 NF P 16-304
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Light intervention cleaning 	Biennial	5%	NF P 16-352 NF P 16-421
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preventive maintenance Curative interventions 	Ten year	8%	NF P 16-422
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heavy intervention Local repair, with excavation if necessary. 	Ten year	from 10 to 50%	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substitution Reparation \ Rehabilitation 	Lifespan From 40 to 50	100%	

The issue of frequent and consecutive failures, i.e., those with a low MTBF (Mean Time Between Failures), should be viewed from the perspective of a lack of scheduled maintenance, which forces to:

- request urgent interventions;
- do not allow the use of all or part of the building;
- preclude the option to seek out the most cost-effective supplies;
- preclude the opportunity to seek out the best repair technician;
- wait for spare parts during the system's downtime;
- Face an ever-increasing failure rate in aging systems.

For all these reasons, real estate/building managers recommend scheduled maintenance to avoid significant disruptions and emergency repairs.

A no-dig technology intervention, such as CIPP, fits well within a building's scheduled maintenance plan, and meet the constraints set by the client.

The maintenance of drainage pipes within a building aims to restore the functional rehabilitation of all or part of the pipe(s). Specifically, a CIPP intervention seeks to:

- Ensure watertightness;
- Reduce the roughness of the pipe's inner walls;
- Guarantee chemical resistance and, if required,
- Provide structural support if the pipe has lost its load-bearing function.

The application of non-destructive techniques offers significant advantages over traditional excavation and demolition methods. Of particular interest to the client are the following benefits:

- Shorter failure resolution times;
- Low environmental impact;
- Reduced total costs;
- Easy setup and dismantling of the site;
- Material savings;
- Minimal equipment footprint, and not least,
- A reduced carbon footprint for the intervention.

In the following paragraphs, we will detail the method.

5. No-dig techniques for discharge pipe rehabilitation

Regardless of the material used in the pipes within a building (plastic, cast iron, steel, stoneware, concrete, asbestos cement, glass-reinforced polyester (GRP) pipes), current non-destructive technologies can be applied. Here, we will only provide a list of these technologies and later focus on the one most used in the maintenance programs of large real estate properties.

No-dig technologies for pipe rehabilitation:

1. Pipes and linings constructed in situ
2. Rehabilitation with close-fit lining
3. Rehabilitation with loose-fit lining

The technologies listed under point 1 are the most widely used, and this category includes the following cases:

- 1.1 Cured-in-place pipes (CIPP)
- 1.2 Cementation
- 1.3 Coating
- 1.4 Linings made of composite materials
- 1.5 Spiral-wound linings.

Very often, pipes within buildings are maintained using a polymerized resin adhered to the internal surface of the host pipe. The CIPP subcategory is further divided into other subcategories based on how the flexible liner is introduced into the host pipe and how the resin is cured.

It should also be noted that the liner can be introduced either with the help of a winch that pulls it inside the pipe, or with an inversion drum that pushes the everted liner into the pipe while inflating it at the same time to make it adhere to the internal surface of the host pipe.

In common installer terminology, the CIPP method is divided into:

1.1 Cured-in-place pipes (CIPP)

1.1.1 UV CIPP and

1.1.2 Thermal CIPP.

This classification refers to the method by which the resin is cured. In **thermal CIPP**, the resin can be cured using steam, hot air, or hot water, while in **UV CIPP**, the resin is hardened by exposure to ultraviolet electromagnetic radiation.

In this dissertation, we will focus on the most widely used method in system maintenance, which is the CIPP method using liner inversion and resin curing with UV lamps.

The liner is the element responsible for transporting the resin, and the resin's function is to provide all the required functional characteristics for the pipe. The typical result of this method is shown in the figure.

Below, we will examine the fundamental components and how they are assembled.

A UV CIPP intervention carried out with a liner made of fiberglass impregnated with photopolymerizing resin also provides structural resistance to the pipe. This technique is not only used for drainage pipes within buildings (rainwater and wastewater pipes) but is also employed in urban and industrial sewers, aqueducts, and gas distribution networks. For each intervention, specific materials have been developed, and the acceptance criteria can be found in the standard UNI EN 13566-4. If structural resistance is required, the thickness calculation can be performed according to the American standard ASTM F 1216-09.

6. CIPP components, equipment and installation procedure

Components. Lining tubes. The liner serves the function of carrying both the resin and itself along the entire length of the pipe to be rehabilitated. It has a composite structure made from materials that provide elasticity, flexibility, strength, liquid permeability and the ability to carry the correct amount of resin.

Liners, with varying thickness and weight, are tubular and can be made from plastics such as polyamide, polyacrylonitrile, and polypropylene, polyurethane sometimes combined with glass fibres. Higher quality liners are made from felt coated with a thermoplastic polyurethane-based product, suitable for giving the final geometry and ensuring the impermeability of the inner membrane.

Lining tubes can be reinforced or flexible.

A fiberglass-reinforced liner provides mechanical properties that can be evaluated through tensile strength and elastic modulus. Below, we provide a comparison table of the mechanical characteristics between fiberglass liner made of E-Glass¹ and polyester felt liners

Elastic modulus of the polyester resin composite

Modulus of elasticity (Mpa)	Fiberglass liner	Polyester felt liner	
		Simple	Fiberglass reinforced
Short-term E	12000	2000	4000
Long-term E	8000	1000	2000

On the other hand, flexibility is a required characteristic for use in sections with changes in diameter or direction, or in a sequence of 90° bends. One of the key requirements for the lining tube is that its length must match that of the host pipe, as joints are not permitted.

Composite tubular

lining tube coil

Inner fabric of the tube

Like all fabrics, lining tubes are characterized by the warp and weft, which affect their thickness and elasticity. The latter is a key requirement for the relining of small-diameter pipes with changes in sections and various curve configurations.

¹ E-Glass Fiber are known for their high stability and durability, and aside from sizing ingredients, they are inorganic, non-combustible, and do not expand or contract with changes in humidity. The glass composition meets the certification for E-glass as defined by ASTM D578-00 Standard Specification for Glass Fiber Strands.

For the rehabilitation of long and large-diameter pipe configurations, the required qualities include resistance under stress, tear resistance, breaking load, elongation at break, and abrasion resistance.

The tubular is made from a sheet made up of several layers of polyester felt to which a layer of polyurethane, impermeable to polyester or vinylester resin, is applied on one of the faces. Generally, several materials are assembled one on top of the other but at the end the edges are turned in such a way that the face coated with polyurethane is external while the felt, which transports the resin, is placed inside. During the inversion of the tubular, the felt then passes to the outside and adheres, through the resin, to the internal surface of the tube to be repaired.

As a final detail, the thickness of the liner, used for the rainwater pipes does not exceed 3 – 3.5 mm, as a greater thickness is uneconomical and does not contribute to improved structural performance of the rainwater pipe.

The lining tube is a composite material, for example, the structure of the flexible tube could consist of a polyester felt coated on one side with a thermoplastic polyurethane film. The liner is tubular in shape and made with seams, reinforcements (i.e. fibers glass) and longitudinal welds. It is suitable for impregnation with epoxy, polyurethane silicate, vinylester and polyester resin with room temperature, LED, steam and hot air curing. It can withstand steam temperatures of up to 80°C. Recommended operating pressure range: 0.2/0.8 atm (depending on the pipe diameter).

During inversion, the lining tube can stretch from 1 to 6% depending on the enlargement undergone and the operating pressures.

Resins. The resin is a fundamental element in the application of CIPP technology, as it serves to fill the annular space between the membrane and the pipe. It must possess certain properties that influence work ergonomics, worker health, and quality before and after curing. Some of these properties include: easy control of polymerization times (pot-life), wettability, adhesion to the substrate, absence of hazardous by-products, leak tightness, chemical resistance, hydraulic smoothness, and abrasion resistance. The mechanical properties of the resin are important in cases where there are sites with differential settlements, as high tensile strength and a high long-term elastic modulus are required.

During the polymerization of the resin, the concentration of styrene increases, and exposure of workers to high concentrations can lead to unconsciousness.

The resins used in CIPP technology are of three types:

- Polyesters
- Vinylesters
- Epoxies.

The resin follows non-Newtonian (thixotropic) behaviour, which makes dripping difficult.

Polyester resin is a two-component material obtained from a vinyl monomer and a polyester. Polyester resins are in liquid form, more or less viscous, translucent in colour with a strong odour due to the presence of styrene.

The polymerization of polyester resins begins with an increase in viscosity and hardens by developing heat. The process is exothermic and the temperature follows the trend as in the figure (SPI Society of the Plastic Industry - USA)

Vinylester resin has a stability to chemical agents. Its use is mainly in the rehabilitation applications of sewer pipes in industrial plants. On the other hand, the cost per unit of weight is higher than that of polyester resin.

Epoxy resins have the advantage of having low shrinkage after polymerization. They have good adhesion to other materials, good resistance to chemical and environmental agents, and good mechanical and electrical insulation properties. The hardening process requires catalysts that can be amines, anhydrides, or aldehydes. Epoxy resin is easy to work with and has a high wetting capacity. From a mechanical point of view, they offer better performance than polyester resins. Due to the lack of release of by-products during hardening, they are also used for the rehabilitation of drinking water pipes.

Generally resins are sensitive to water; in fact, among the recommendations from resin manufacturers is to use them in dry environments. On the other hand, epoxy resin exceeds this limitation and it doesn't realise dangerous products (styrene) during hardening. Considering all the properties mentioned, the cost of epoxy resin is 3 to 4 times that of standard polyester or vinylester resins. The significant cost of epoxy resin is a major limitation for its use in sewer rehabilitation.

Below is the technical data sheet for a two-component resin (A+B) which can be used on liner made of natural or synthetic fibres with a polyamine-based hardener, featuring a slow curing time.

7. Technical Data Sheets

Technical Data Sheet for Relining Applications

<i>Features</i>	<i>Measure unit</i>	<i>Values</i>
Specific weight	Kg/dm ³	Ca 1.20
Stoichiometric ratio in weight	A:B =	80:20
Pot life	minutes	About 45
Time of first curing mm 2 at 25 ±2°C (only resin)	hours	About 5.30
Curing time on FAP 400 at 20±2°C	hours	About 3.5
Unitary breaking load for flexotraction*	MPa	>75
Elastic module for flexotraction*	GPa	>2.6

Below is the technical data sheet for a two-component resin (A+B) with a polyamine-based hardener, featuring a rapid curing time and capable of repairing a pipe in one hour.

Technical Data Sheet for coating applications

<i>Features</i>	<i>Measure unit</i>	<i>Values</i>
Specific weight	Kg/dm ³	Ca 1.27
Stoichiometric ratio in weight	A:B =	100:80
Pot life	minutes	About 3
Time of first curing mm 2 at 25 ±2°C	hours	About 1.5
Time of restarting pipe service with water contact 20 ±2°C	hours	About 1.5
Unitary breaking load for flexotraction*	MPa	>60
Elastic module for flexotraction*	GPa	>2.8

Generally, at lower temperature (i.e. 10°C) the working is more difficult for the increase the viscosity on the contrary, at higher temperature the product may drastically lower the pot lifetimes. It is therefore advisable to cool the mixture before the use.

8. Resin consumption

As regards the consumption of resin per metre of length of ready-to-use product, the following table is provided

<i>t</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>DN</i> <i>30</i>	<i>DN</i> <i>40</i>	<i>DN</i> <i>50</i>	<i>DN</i> <i>60</i>	<i>DN</i> <i>70</i>	<i>DN</i> <i>80</i>	<i>DN</i> <i>100</i>	<i>DN</i> <i>110</i>	<i>DN</i> <i>120</i>	<i>DN</i> <i>150</i>	<i>DN</i> <i>200</i>
2,5	5,5	0,261	0,350	0,390	0,551	0,611		1,012	0,922			
3	6,5	0,301		0,481	0,541	0,700		1,012				
4	8,5				0,831	0,922	1,092	1,313		0,176	0,231	
5	10,5										0,295	0,428

It should be noted that twice the nominal thickness of the liner is less than the space between the rollers of the machine used to apply the resin. This distance represents a compromise between the correct amount of resin that should be deposited on the inner surface of the liner and the force required to pull it manually.

9. Installation procedure.

Preliminary and preparatory operations for rehabilitation intervention is mandatory, the pipe is to prepared with the following steps:

1. Taking the pipe out of service
2. Preliminary video inspection
3. Mechanical cleaning of the downpipe

4. In-situ liner impregnation
5. Lining tube insertion
6. Cured with UV Lamp
7. Preparation of any lateral connections, if present.

The pipe have to be deactivated by disconnecting from the drainage system.

The preliminary video inspection, different from the diagnostic inspection, aims to identify any obstacles that could hinder the proper insertion of the liner inside the pipe, and to detect any lateral connections.

A thorough cleaning of the downpipe has to be performed by heavy metal brushes to remove debris, including those adhered to the internal surface.

Before being impregnated with resin, the liner must be vacuumed using vacuum pumps to allow the resin to adequately penetrate the liner. This operation can be done *in situ* when using small-diameter pipes and epoxy resins; otherwise, the process is carried out in a factory using machinery.

Resins naturally harden with temperature, so a catalyst is introduced into the flexible tube to increase the pot-life. For thermosetting resins, the impregnated liner can be stored in a refrigerator and used within 3-4 days. In contrast, when using UV-curing resins, they must be stored in sealed, light-proof containers.

The pre-processed liner thus has the internal support (polyester felt) impregnated with resin. The inversion machine's task is to turn the tube inside out so that the resin-coated side adheres to the internal surface of the pipe to be repaired.

The machine operator has to monitor the pressure in the lining tube, during eversion or inflation is sufficient to hold it tight to the pipe wall and prevent any internal deformation of the lining tube. The constant pressure for the tube everted is achieved by a low-power air compressor.

In order to a photo cure of the resin the operator has to adopt an Ultra-Violet lamp reducing significantly the curing time of applied resins. The use of a lamp that provides a certain emission, the right power and an adequate speed of the lamp shooting inside the tube allow to control the hardening process and guarantee a uniform hardening time.

In the rehabilitation of sewage pipes, a pre-liner is sometimes used to prevent resin contamination by water, as some resins do not cure when in contact with water.

At the end of the curing process, the liner must be trimmed at the end, and the downpipe must be connected to the system. A final inspection and testing shall be executed.

10. Tools required for carrying out a CIPP intervention

Essential equipment for an installer are:

- Device for cleaning metal pipes;
- Roller device for applying resin;
- Inversion drum;
- Equipment for maintaining and monitoring pressure;
- UV light source for cure epoxy resin;
- Finishing equipment such as a robotic cutter for opening lateral connection;

Among the machines above listed the inversion drum for relining is notable and it consists of the following components:

1. Loading hatch for the resin-impregnated liner;
2. Winding shaft;
3. Motor for moving the winding shaft inside the machine;
4. Controls for various movements;
5. Wheels for movement.

Optional fittings are:

Valves and connectors for air input; Valves and connectors for steam input necessary for resin curing in the liner; Thermometer; Safety valves; Pressure gauge

Before applying the lining, it is essential to prepare the surface with mechanical cleaning. Depending on the situation, brushes and/or chains may be suitable. The use of high-pressure water (canal jet) is not always recommended for corroded pipes or those with adhered limescale.

The loading of the liner into the inversion drum must be performed with simultaneous lubrication. It should be noted that perfect adhesion of the liner to the internal surface of the host pipe is only achievable with proper application of the resin to the felt. Before being impregnated with resin, the liner must be vacuumed using vacuum pumps to allow the resin to adequately penetrate the material. Any excess resin is removed using a pinch roller.

The next steps is to cure the resin by UV lamps. The UV light resin curing device can be automated to maintain a constant speed, which ranges from a few meters per hour, e.g., 10 m/h for DN 300 up to 110 m/h for DN 70. To reduce the required electrical power, while maintaining the same emission level, the lamps are of the LED type.

Wire brush

Rotary chain cutter

Canal jet

Pinch rollers

Manual roller

Simple inversion drum

Inversion drum combined with curing lamp.

Air compressor

rigid compressed air pipe

Coil of rigid compressed air pipe

Pulling cable

Light source for UV radiation emission

Several lamp size

Lateral opening device for destruction of cured liner

Lateral opening for milling

Normative references

- | | |
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| ASTM F 1216-9 | Standard Practice for rehabilitation of existing pipeline and conduits by the inversion and curing of a resin-impregnated tube |
| ASTM D578-00 | Standard Specification for Glass Fiber Strands |

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